

Restating theories of biological function as algorithms

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WHATIF

WASWÄREWENN

ON THE MEANING, RELEVANCE,
AND EPISTEMOLOGY OF
COUNTERFACTUAL CLAIMS AND
THOUGHT EXPERIMENTS

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Overview

- 1 Introduction
- 2 Why theories of biological function should be restated as algorithms
- 3 Two examples
 - 1 Etiological theory
 - 2 Propensity theory
- 4 Conclusion and outlook

Theories of biological function (TBFs) – a wild crowd

- Etiological theory (Wright 1973, Millikan 1989, Neander 1991)
- Propensity theory (Bigelow & Pargetter 1987)
- Systemic theory (Cummins 1976, Craver 2001)
- Goal-oriented theory (McLaughlin 2001, Mossio et al. 2009)
- Biostatistical theory (Boorse 1975, Garson & Piccinini 2013)
- Modal theory (Canfield 1966, Nanay 2010)
- and so on

TBFs are theories about what?

A TBF can be taken to answer any of the following questions:

- What is a biological function?
 - ▶ Metaphysical project
 - ▶ A biological function is...
- What does the concept *biological function* mean?
 - ▶ Semantic project
 - ▶ *Biological function* refers to or means...
- How is the concept *function* used in biology?
 - ▶ Descriptive project
 - ▶ *Function* is used in biology to refer to...

Two methodological observations

Observation 1

TBFs should be applicable to biological practice in the metaphysical, semantic and descriptive project.

- Biological practice refers to list of paradigmatic examples of function ascription
 - ▶ “The p53 gene has the function to brake the cycle of cell growth” (Vogelstein et al. 2000), more than 4700 citations
 - ▶ “Control of apoptosis is only part of the gene's [i.e., p53] function – though a very important part” (Alberts et al. 2007), standard textbook on the molecular biology of the cell
- TBF applicable to biological practice only if definite answer wrt function ascription is provided for all paradigmatic examples
- Without applicability relevance of TBFs is hard to see

Two methodological observations

Observation 2

Operational criteria guarantee the applicability of TBFs to biological practice.

- Notion of operational criteria is an epistemic notion; it refers to the instructions to carry out a process
- Operational criteria can be made explicit by means of an algorithm
 - ▶ Definite and finite step-by-step procedure
 - ▶ High-level description
 - ▶ Complexity, error-handling etc. ignored

My claim and why you might care

Claim

TBFs should be restated as algorithms in order to guarantee their applicability to biological practice.

Why is this interesting?

- Surprisingly many TBFs are not applicable to biological practice
 - ▶ Operational underspecification
 - ▶ Definitional underspecification
- Restating TBFs as algorithms reveals reliance on biological modality
- Biological modality is yet only rudimentarily understood

Algorithm represented as flowchart

Data symbols

Process symbols

Line symbols

Restating the etiological theory as an algorithm

- “The definition of ‘proper function’ is recursive.” (Millikan 1989, 288)
- “An etiological theory of functions claims that what counts as a function of a trait is determined by that trait’s history. [...] In my view, the central element of the etiological approach should be seen as the simple idea that a function of a trait is the effect for which that trait was selected.” (Neander 1991, 459)

Restating the etiological theory as an algorithm

Restating the etiological theory as an algorithm

- Blackboxed processes rely on counterfactuals exactly if historical data is not available
 - ▶ Historical data is usually not readily available
 - ▶ Some exceptions in vitro, e.g. *E. coli* long-term evolution experiment
- 'How-possibly' rather than 'how-actually' model

Restating the propensity theory as an algorithm

- The etiological theory describes a character now as serving a function, when it did confer propensities that improved the chances of survival. We suggest that it is appropriate, in such a case, to say that the character has been serving that function all along. Even before it had contributed (in an appropriate way) to survival, it had conferred a survival-enhancing propensity on the creature. And to confer such a propensity, we suggest, is what constitutes a function. (Bigelow and Pargetter 1987, 192)
 - ▶ Propensity is a stochastically interpreted disposition
 - ▶ Propensity to survive (and reproduce) increases life chances

Restating the propensity theory as an algorithm

Restating the propensity theory as an algorithm

- How are life chances influenced?
 - ▶ Determine population; counterfactual comparison
 - ▶ Determine environment; biological normality
- How are life chances determined?
 - ▶ Computational model of selection process
 - ▶ Biological thought-experiment

Conclusion

- TBFs may be part of different projects; all projects require applicability of TBFs to biological practice
- One way to guarantee applicability is by restating TBFs as algorithms
- TBFs are operationally (and sometimes definitionally) underspecified
- Etiological theory relies on biological modality due to epistemic constraints
- Propensity theory makes inherent use of biological modality
- Future work:
 - ▶ How to make restatement of TBFs mathematically precise?
 - ▶ How to restate other TBFs? How is biological modality involved?
 - ▶ How make restated TBFs better sense of biological practice?

THANK YOU!

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